

The Heart of Learning: Embracing Moral Education in Today's Schools

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Abstract

Moral education is essential in developing learners' character and fostering social cohesion. Education systems worldwide focus on providing moral values and virtues to students to develop morally upright citizens. However, achieving this goal most effectively is still challenging, with different opinions on which solutions would be most beneficial. The study aims to explore the function of moral education in schools, concentrating on its influence on student character development and addressing its associated problems and positive aspects through qualitative research. To conduct this study, 27 respondents were interviewed, including in-depth interviews (IDI), key informant interviews (KII), and focus group discussions (FGD) sessions, with the participation of teachers, experts, and parents. This qualitative research used purposive sampling and created a semi-structured questionnaire for interviews. The findings of this study show that schools play a crucial role in shaping children's moral character by providing social experiences and teaching skills like honesty, sympathy, and responsibility. Schools place equal emphasis on moral education and academic achievement, emphasizing inclusivity, friendliness, and respect. Character education programs, disciplinary policies, and community involvement help students develop social responsibility. However, excessive focus on academic outcomes faces challenges such as cultural and religious diversity and social pressures. In addition, the benefits of moral education include exposure to sound principles, improved social relationships, sympathy, social responsibility, and citizenship. Moral principles shape compassionate individuals who will enrich society through thoughtful action and responsible citizenship.

Keywords: Moral education, character development, ethical values, social-emotional learning (SEL), school culture.

INTRODUCTION

Students' basic knowledge and character are greatly influenced by their primary school education (Mara, 2025). The effectiveness of principals' leadership in running and directing schools has a significant impact on the quality of elementary education. Education has a significant impact on human existence (Afni et al., 2024). It is acknowledged that education is a powerful tool that can help people appreciate the beauty and progress of civilization. In addition, education prepares students for a more compassionate and promising future (Getteng, 2021; Sitopu et al., 2024). Since education is the only way for individuals to acquire the information and skills necessary to manage the nature that God has given us, the topic of education ranks among the most significant and pressing issues of our day (Antika et al., 2024). According to this assertion, education has a significant role in a people's moral growth, wealth, and even prosperity. Thus, the degree of education may be used to gauge the development of a population or a country (Daradjat, 2017).

The implementation of moral principles into classroom management has emerged as an essential strategy for dealing with both academic and behavioural issues in education (Tumiran et al., 2025). Values-based education promotes students' academic development as well as their social and emotional intelligence. This comprehensive strategy guarantees that students are not only academically competent but also responsible, empathic, and socially active citizens (Pham, 2024). In the current era characterized by globalization and digitalization, the challenges in moral education are becoming more complex (Sanger & Osguthorpe, 2013). Students are exposed to various negative influences from social networks, the internet, and technology that can affect their moral values. With the various conveniences and freedoms of using the internet, it is important to instil good and correct values in students through character and moral education to translate abstract principles about moral character regard to overcome the phenomenal problems of attitude and behaviour that exist in the current era (Mustoip et al., 2018). As a result, moral education

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is becoming more and more important to ensure that students are not only intellectually intelligent but also possess strong integrity and ethics (Nucci et al., 2014). Moral education aims not only to cultivate knowledgeable individuals but also to develop good and moral character (Narvaez & Lapsley, 2009).

Hence, moral education is essential in developing learners' character and fostering social cohesion. Education systems worldwide focus on providing moral values and virtues to students to develop morally upright citizens, but achieving this goal most effectively is still a challenge, with different opinions on which solutions would be most beneficial (Tang & Wang, 2021). The United States of America emphasizes moral education, but has joint problems, such as school violence (Nyangaresi et al., 2024). In Bangladesh, moral education is increasingly acknowledged as critical for holistic development, with the Ministry of Education putting ethics into the curriculum for grades 6 and 7, to promote global citizenship and sustainable development (Tasnim, 2025). Character education is linked to morals. A nation's morals will improve if the students have good character and moral principles. To develop a moral country, students must get a moral education (Asif et al., 2020). This requires involvement in the family, school, and community (Birhan et al., 2021). Children who are educated and fostered using parents, education, and a positive environment grow up to be noble and exceptional individuals (Islamiyah et al., 2025). Responsibility encourages students to always be courageous in carrying out their obligations and facing the repercussions of their actions. Parents and instructors provide examples and stimuli concerning responsibility to children, how children should behave in response to the task handed down to them, and the issues they confront (Suciati et al., 2023).

However, many studies at the national and international levels on Embracing Moral Education have attempted to find out their roles in morality and ethics, moral education, moral education integrated into the curriculum, etc. (Arjanto et al., 2025; Dawam et al., 2025; Istiyani et al., 2024; Mahmudulhassan et al., 2024; Nyangaresi et al., 2024; Sayfullayevna, 2024; Tasnim, 2025; Zahira et al., 2024). Building upon prior studies on this particular topic, there is hardly any significant research on the status of moral education in schools in Bangladesh today, as the objective of this study.

Therefore, in this study, we were exploring the function of moral education in schools, concentrating on its influence on student character development and addressing its associated

problems and positive aspects through qualitative research. Since the fourth sustainable development objective is to provide quality education, while the sixteenth is aimed at encouraging peace, justice, and strong institutions. So, moral and ethical education are essential components of quality education because they influence students' conduct and actions. This study will assist in determining the gap between teacher training, teaching, and actual practices for establishing moral principles in Bangladeshi primary schools. Also, it may reflect the mentality of teachers and parents regarding current malpractices in elementary education, such as duplication and cheating in tests. This study will assist in understanding the thinking of teachers and parents, together with national curriculum goals, on developing a just nation by teaching moral principles in elementary school.

METHOD

Research type and design of the study

The study used a basic interpretative research approach, and the data was qualitative. In this study, data were collected using a qualitative research technique to fulfil the study's aims. The primary goal of employing a qualitative research technique was to elicit more detailed information from the key informants. According to Creswell (2013), when a thorough understanding of a crucial phenomenon is required, the qualitative approach is used in research. As a result, the current study employed a qualitative research approach to gain a deeper understanding of the research topic. According to qualitative approaches, deep discussion has made it possible to find out the authentic result.

Sample size

As a researcher, the researcher believes that merely collecting 27 samples will correctly reflect the study's goal. Because Clarke & Braun (2013) advised sample sizes of at least 12 individuals. According to Hagaman and Wutich (2016), we determined that 16 interviews or less were enough to find common themes in regions with very homogeneous populations.

Furthermore, in this study, the researcher was allowed to collect data from people of his choice, and the researcher collected data according to the objectives of the study. Among them were 10 school teachers who teach in the school, and data were collected from them through in-depth interviews (IDIs), 10 head teachers, and 5 experts who work on ethical perspectives; data were collected through key informant interviews (KIIs). Finally, two

Table 1. Sample distribution of the study

Sample	Sample Size	Sampling	Instruments
KIIs (Key Informant Interviews)		Purposive	Semi-structured questionnaire for in-depth interviews
Head Teachers	10		
Moral Education Experts	5		
IDIs (Individual In-depth Interviews)		Purposive	Semi-structured questionnaire for in-depth interviews
Teachers	10		
FGDs (Focus Group Discussions)		Purposive	In-depth interview questionnaire for FGDs
Parents	2 FGD's (7+7=14 participants)		

focus group discussions (FGDs) were held, and 7 people were present on both teams (see Table 1).

Sampling technique and questionnaire design

To accomplish the desired sample size, a purposive sampling strategy was applied. In this case, the researcher relied only on his judgment and conscience to proceed. That is, the focus here is on personal judgment rather than numbers. Purposive sampling was used since this research required far more expert information. The researcher chose semi-structured questions for the interview. A semi-structured interview combines the benefits of both a structured and an unstructured interview.

Purposeful sampling relies on the researcher's judgment when choosing study participants, which is why it is also referred to as judgment, selective, or subjective sampling. A non-probability sampling technique called "purposeful sampling" selects sample items based on the researcher's opinion. Researchers often believe that they can obtain a representative sample and save time and money by using excellent judgment (Black, 2023).

Data processing and analysis

To examine the data, he gathered, the researcher employed thematic analysis of writing. Since thematic analysis is a technique for analyzing qualitative data, it is typically used on a collection of texts, such as interview transcripts. To identify recurring themes, subjects, concepts, and situational patterns, the researcher carefully examines the data. Thematic analysis is among the most popular forms of analysis in qualitative research (Christou, 2022). The researcher analyzed the information that he received, according to the 6 steps of Braun and Clarke. According to Braun and Clarke (2006), thematic analysis is a method for detecting, interpreting, and reporting patterns (themes) within data.

RESULTS

This chapter provides a thorough review of the data analysis and study findings. Based on the purpose of the study, the researcher collected data from a variety of samples, which is discussed in this chapter. This is explained below based on thematic analysis on the purpose. The primary themes of the study are as follows: 1. The Role of Schools in Shaping Moral Character, 2. Challenges to Moral Education, 3. And the Benefits of Moral Education:

1. The Role of schools in shaping moral character: Moral development for children is greatly assisted by the school's guidance, as these children receive social experience such as friendship formation, problem-solving, and facing the socio-cultural environment. Additionally, students learn techniques to deal with the problems within the boundaries of honesty, sympathy, and responsibility.

1.1. Teacher-student relationships: Teachers not only pass on their academic knowledge as information, but also use their experience as a teacher to educate on the impact of morality in a person's life. They exhibit notions and practices of good

moral behavior that students tend to follow blindly. KII- Ex 03+04 said that.

"Moral character can be instilled in a learner through the teacher's strong exhibition of respect, integrity, and authority".

Moreover, Teachers can assist students in thinking through complex civic problems and moral choices. Rather, teachers can help in the moderation of conflicts between students and attempt to resolve the problem in a way that encourages responsibility and care. Theta can help students understand what is good or bad and why it is significant, and how to employ morality in various situations.

1.2. School culture and climate: The moral affiliation of a community is deeply impacted by the culture of the school. A sound school culture focuses on inclusion, friendliness, and respect. When these values are part of the school culture, children feel valued, safe, and supported. IDI-T05 + FGD-02 said that.

"School is the kind of environment where students are motivated to appreciate moral values and understand their importance in everyday life".

For example, schools that implement restorative practices cultivate empathy and responsibility by having students take responsibility for the harm they have caused and make amends. In the same way, those educational institutions that care for students, promote group decision making, and let students take up leadership roles make it very clear that moral character is vital not just for the individuals but also for the society.

1.3. Character / disciplinary policy education programs: Several schools are also incorporating character education programs into their calendars. These courses are meant to teach students accountability, sympathy, integrity, and diligence. Schools may teach moral development through special courses, or they may teach character education as part of other classes.

In programs like 'Second Step' and 'Positive Behavioral Interventions and Supports (PBIS),' students develop social-emotional skills like self-regulation, decision-making, and conflict resolution. KII-HT03 said that,.

"Such strategies support students to reflect on their behavior and realize how their actions affect others, and help them cultivate social responsibility through organized lessons and activities".

And the way a school administers discipline also impacts students' moral development. Disciplinary systems that offer restorative rather than punitive justice, by forcing students to reflect upon their behaviour and the pain they have caused, help students learn sympathy and accountability. Simply administering discipline without explanation may fail to teach students the higher moral lessons. Students are urged to "consider how to make apologies" and "avoid making the same errors again," using restorative techniques such as getting them involved in discussing their behavior and its effects on others.

This technique promotes accountability and personal development in addition to delivering moral teachings.

1.4. Ethical decision-making through curriculum: School curriculum can also directly affect moral development among children. By exposing students to ethical dilemmas, educators can encourage students to consider ethical principles. For instance, lessons in literature often provide the opportunity to analyze the choices that characters make as well as the outcomes of these choices. FGD-01+02 also said that,

“By discussing morally sound decisions used by people in stories they read, history classes discuss, or news stories they hear, students learn to think about the ethical questions involved and the complexity of morality”.

Although science programs may instruct students on the ethical haze of technical advances, history inquiries can explore the consequences of inequity. KII- HT07 said that,

“When you frame discussions of ethical problem-solving in multiple topic areas, students understand that ethics cannot be compartmentalized and that ethical issues stem from all aspects of life and human interaction and decision-making”.

1.5. Community engagement and service learning: IDI-T09 said that,

“Another important way that schools help students develop moral character is through community involvement and service-learning actions”.

Students who engage in community service programs receive a firsthand view of how helping others improves the quality of life in society. Via service learning, Service learning involves students in activities that address community needs while reflecting on the impact of their experience, allowing them to get to know the world around them in a social responsibility and hear some moral commitment. These encounters teach students about social justice issues and the importance of sympathy and compassion. KII-Ex-05 also said that,

“Volunteering instills a sense of responsibility to others and fosters in students a fuller awareness of the challenges people face, whether they are working at a food bank, tutoring younger students, or participating in environmental projects”.

1.5. Social interactions and peer relationships: These peer contacts are one of the numerous ways schools can create moral character. In school, children spend a good amount of time with other children performing group tasks, socializing, and other activities. In these activities, children learn skills that help them build sincere relationships, learn how to resolve conflicts, and handle differences. Through negotiating bonds of friendship, group dynamics, and peer disputes, adolescents begin to understand the values of sympathy, concern, and regard.

Students, for example, need to cultivate respect and association during group work since they get exposed to other perspectives. These everyday encounters make children learn about justice, compromise, and appreciate different perspectives, be it while

engaging in playground games or through collaboration in class projects. This indicates that schools provide a constructive environment for developing social motor skills and ethical attitudes in human beings.

2. Challenges to moral education: Educational institutions should establish environments where moral debates can happen openly and students learn to appreciate diversity alongside essential values such as compassion, fairness, and respect. The process of integrating moral education into educational institutions poses multiple challenges despite its vital role in student development. These challenges should motivate us to develop teaching methods that consider everyone's needs while instilling core values. Institutional frameworks, along with cultural and practical issues, create barriers for schools to focus on character development and execute moral education programs. These represent some of the principal barriers.

2.1. Lack of time and focus in the curriculum: Educational institutions usually place math, science, reading, and writing at the forefront of their curriculum, especially when students need to prepare for state or national standardized tests. IDI-T04+10 said that,

“The heavy focus on academic results and standardized testing within numerous educational systems stands as a primary barrier to effective moral education”.

FGD-01 also said,

“Character building has a low chance of being engrained in students due to the lack of proper facilities like an appropriate classroom size, modern teaching aids and extracurricular activities”.

Moral education, often considered secondary to intellectual achievements, ends up with minimal space in school programs. Educational institutions and teachers face challenges when they need to fit moral education into the crowded school curriculum. Educators recognize the importance of teaching values such as integrity, deference, and sympathy, but their efforts are often limited by time constraints and the necessity to meet testing requirements and cover various academic subjects. Moral education becomes an afterthought or optional component in learning rather than being recognized as fundamental to education.

2.2. Cultural and religious diversity: Today, schools cater to a broader demographic that includes students of varied cultural, ethnic, and religious backgrounds. While this variety is positive for education, it makes teaching universal ethical values much more difficult. What is defined as “moral” or “ethical” can vary greatly depending on cultural, religious, and familial standards. For instance, different groups can perceive the concepts of individualism vs syndicalism, authority vs autonomy, or even gender equality quite differently. When it comes to moral issues in the classroom, teachers have to be very careful. If left unstructured, ethical teaching can create polarization and alienation for those students who do not share the same perspective as the school. FGDs-02 also said that,

“In this regard, schools need to focus on teaching ethical values of respect, justice, sympathy, and even legal services while at the same time encouraging students to learn about and accept other opinions”.

Nevertheless, maintaining balance between global and culturally specific values can be quite difficult.

2.3. Inconsistent support and training for teachers: Most educators have some training in character development or moral education. KII-Ex05 said that,

“Even if value education is something that many educators are born with a zeal for, many do not have the requisite materials, equipment, or even the necessary pedagogical skill set to integrate moral education into their lessons”.

Teachers may lack the proper support and training to deal with value judgments of enactment of moral behavior or discussions of values in the class setting.

Moreover, courses aimed at enhancing professional competencies with an emphasis on moral education are often absent. KII-HT06 also said that.

“Teachers might need help in solving sensitive moral issues such as bullying, discrimination, or even conflict that stems from different ethical positions held by students”.

In the absence of this support, teachers would find it hard to create an environment that fosters moral development, or may opt not to teach morals altogether to avoid the troubles.

2.4. Parental and community involvement: Moral education should take in parents and all other members of society, other than the school. As already indicated, moral education does present conflicts due to the varying opinions, beliefs, and expectations of the parents or other community members. FGD-02 said that,

“Some parents may hold strong views about 'good' moral education, which more often than not conflicts with the set standards in the schools, or opt to teach moral education themselves”.

Parents who tend to be more traditional or old-fashioned will not support schools that promote diversity and inclusion. In the same way, due to political debates, sexuality debates, or climate change debates, parents and teachers may fight over how ethical teachings should be delivered.

If schools are to break through these walls, they must first have good connections with families and the community. This means allowing frank communications, but also giving parents a chance to voice their opinion about the role of moral education in the teaching process. KII-Ex02 also said.

“Equally important is that colleges and universities enact policies and programs that embody the communal values of these ethical boundaries and the community”.

2.5. Negative peer influence and societal pressures: IDI-09+ KII-HT03 said that,

“The pressure to fit in with peers may at times go against the values taught in schools, and students may find it difficult to relate to the moral lessons instilled in them while facing bullying, cheating, and other negative activities”.

Furthermore, wider social pressures like social media, popular cultural trends, and even the media can send mixed signals about moral values. Social media, for instance, tends to promote materialism, shallowness, and the desire to fulfill one's needs immediately, counteracting the school's mandates of responsibility, sympathy, and integrity.

To address such external influences, schools may implement programs aimed at helping the students increase their self-efficacy, resilience, and critical thinking skills. KII-Ex04 also said.

“Equipped with the ability to resist social and media influences, students can better manage their behaviors in morally challenging situations”.

2.6. Emotional and behavioral challenges: Peer pressure may, at some point, challenge the moral values instilled in schools, and students may find it difficult to reconcile their actions with the morals they learn in school, which could range from bullying, cheating, and other adverse behaviours. Also, the influence of social media, popular culture, and the media puts additional wider societal pressures that often send mixed moral signals. Particularly in social media, materialism, superficiality, and instant gratification are frequently glorified, which contradict the school's effort in fostering sympathy, responsibility, and integrity. IDI-T01 said that,

“To mitigate these external forces, schools can establish programs that promote self-awareness, resilience, and critical thinking skills”.

KII-HT07 also said.

“Such skills enable students to resist peer pressure and media influence so that even in difficult socio-contextual situations, they can adhere to their moral conduct”.

3. The benefits of moral education: To address these challenges, schools are advocating for opportunities for moral and social emotional learning within the curriculum and efforts to realign the objectives of education with the holistic development of the child rather than solely academically oriented objectives. Below are the solutions to the problem discussed based on the opinions of the participants:

3.1. Improved social relationships and conflict resolution:

Through moral education, sympathy has been inculcated, which is a component of building strong, healthy relationships with other individuals. Shared feelings and cooperation are encouraged by moral education. KII-HT04 said that,

“Due to training in understanding and caring about the emotions and opinions of others, students are better at handling peer interaction”.

The sensitivity resulting from sympathy helps students work better at home and in the larger community. KII-Ex03 also said.

Through moral education, values of repentance, compromise, and positive communication are inculcated, which in the long run will be cornerstone values for the student. The students become better navigators of conflict, are less likely to turn to bullying, exclusion, or violence and other negative behaviors in times of conflict”.

3.2. Promotion of social responsibility and citizenship:

Students are to consider their social role and their responsibilities to the members of society-in other words, the notion of the other is taught through moral education. IDI-T07 said that,

“Schools help students build a sense of social responsibility that goes beyond their immediate self-interest by teaching them about justice, fairness, and civic obligation”.

Otherwise, without a sense of community there to implement this, how would the pupils be encouraged to do something constructive back into their environments? Students from whom the requisite knowledge on social justice, for instance, is obtained could prefer to work to minimize challenges of inequality, poverty, or the environment. More inclined behaviors will also follow, towards benefiting society as a whole, changing precisely this appearance as well as giving back to the community. KII-HT02 also said that,

“Such a sense of social responsibility nurtures individuals into active, engaged ones who are dedicated to bettering the world”.

3.3. Reduction in negative behavior and delinquency:

Moral education and social-emotional learning have been empirically validated to decrease the probability of students engaging in such problematic behaviors as delinquency, substance abuse, or bullying. KII-Ex03 said that,

“Ethical education fosters strengthening the character-building process, which enhances the prospects for students to make sound ethical judgments through values such as respect, sympathy, or responsibility”.

FGDs-01 also said that.

“When students know how to behave, the consequences that come with their acts, and how to resolve conflicts constructively, they will not indulge themselves in harmful behaviors”.

This will play a significant role in promoting a safer and supportive school climate since, in such conditions, students do not easily get involved in violent or antisocial behaviors.

3.4. Improved academic performance: The aim of moral education is not really to join and help the child's academic performance. There is an immediate relationship between

students' moral attitudinal growth and their academic achievement. Academic achievement seems more with moral principles that are strong in a student since he becomes a disciplined person, team-player, and takes a keen interest in the work assigned to him in class. These naturally increase motivation, attentiveness, and actual academic achievement. Students are more likely to strive to achieve academically if they feel that their school environment is fair, respectful, and inclusive. KII- HT02 said that,

“If they have a sense that the value of hard work and being responsible is inculcated within them, they will likely be more persistent in their studies and strive for success”.

IDI-T03 also said.

“It is in striving for success, considering efforts and commitments that they can display the values of moral education”.

3.5. Encouragement of self-reflection and personal growth:

Students who receive moral education are motivated to think about their views, actions, and their impact on others. This process of introspection is crucial for personal growth because it allows students to assess their behaviors, learn from their failures and make informed decisions moving forward. KII-Ex04 said that,

“Moral education helps students develop to think critically about moral issues and ethical choices, and to create a robust moral identity”.

For, along with understanding right from wrong, students gain a more profound sense of their values and perspectives by understanding the why of these differences.

3.6. Development of ethical and responsible individuals:

One of the chief benefits of moral education is the exposure of human beings to sound principles and well-behaved characters. Basic values that include honesty, integrity, respect, justice, and accountable are taught to kids at an early age. With age, these values become part of them and increase the chances of behaving well and taking responsibility in school now and later on in life. Students who know what honesty is will therefore, in their personal, professional life, and for academic work (say, by avoiding plagiarism in exam answers), act more honestly. IDI-T08 said that,

“A student who understands what equity means will approach disagreements and relationships with a sense of equity and justice”.

3.7. Inclusive school climate and long-term impact on society:

When schools start placing moral instruction at the top of the order, the atmosphere immediately becomes more positive, and inclusive. Pupils are encouraged to practice inclusivity, appreciate variety and accept opposing viewpoints. KII-HT06 said that,

“This cultivates an environment where all students, no matter where they come from or the way they are different from others, get to know appreciated, are heard, and respected”.

No bullying, discrimination, or exclusion occurs in schools with an inclusive climate, which also makes the school friendlier to all children. FGD-01 also said,

“Any moral education promotes respect for others, which helps build social and emotional skills needed to work with people and navigate the complexities of contexts”.

Long-term benefits exist far beyond the classroom for moral education, which can impact society as a whole. You would expect students who learn moral values and proper decision-making skills to grow into people who make social contributions. They are more likely to vote, volunteer, behave in pro-social ways, and make decisions that benefit society at large instead of just themselves. When practiced consistently, moral education helps in developing a more responsible, empathetic, and fairer society. When people have the tools to act with integrity, resolve conflict decisively, and determine what is right and wrong, they help create a more compassionate and cooperative environment.

DISCUSSION

Role of schools in shaping moral character

Moral character is an important part of how children grow up, and schools have a big impact on how this character develops. According to Madelo's (2015) research, schools offer social experiences that help students develop qualities like honesty, empathy, and responsibility. These experiences include problem-solving, friendship-building, and interacting with the sociocultural environment. However, moral education is often overlooked due to competing priorities such as revenue generation, standardised testing, or academic achievement. The universal values of honesty, equity, and respect transcend all family backgrounds, and schools are uniquely positioned to put them into practice.

Schools should understand the moral and ethical upbringing of children's welfare, even when the classroom revolves around the subject of focus. Similarly, Daud et al. (2023) mentioned in his research that social interactions and peer relationships are one way schools can create moral character. Students spend a lot of time with other children performing group tasks, socials, and other activities, learning skills that help them build sincere relationships, resolve conflicts, and handle differences (Folgeet al., 2021). Teachers not only pass on their academic knowledge but also use their experience as a teacher to educate on the impact of morality in a person's life. As Haduong et al. (2019) pointed out in their research, they can help students think through complex civic problems and moral choices, encouraging responsibility and care.

School culture and climate deeply impact moral affiliation, with a sound school culture focusing on inclusion, friendliness, and respect. When these values are part of the school culture, children feel valued, safe, and supported. Schools that implement restorative practices cultivate sympathy and

responsibility by having students take responsibility for the harm they have caused and make amends.

Character education programs like 'Second Step' and 'Positive Behavioral Interventions and Supports (PBIS)' teach students accountability, sympathy, integrity, and diligence. As Harte (2017) mentioned in their study, these strategies support students to reflect on their behavior and realize how their actions affect others, helping them cultivate social responsibility through organized lessons and activities.

Students' moral growth is also affected by rules and punishments. Schools should offer restorative justice, which would make students think about what they did and how it hurt other people. Ethical decision-making through the curriculum can also directly affect moral development among children.

Lastly, service learning and community service are two important ways that schools help students grow morally. Students learn firsthand how helping others makes the world a better place by taking part in community service programs. Service learning requires students to engage in activities that meet community needs while reflecting on the impact of their experiences, fostering a socially responsible understanding of the world and a sense of moral obligation.

Challenges to moral education

Moral education is a crucial aspect of student development, but it faces several challenges. These include the heavy focus on academic results and standardized testing, as Subban et al. (2025) noted in their research, the growing diversity in student demographics, and the need for teachers to adapt their teaching methods to accommodate the diverse needs of students. The absence of time and focus in the curriculum is a significant obstacle to moral education (Bourke, 2019).

Schools often put more emphasis on maths, science, reading, and writing than on moral education, making it an optional part of learning. This can lead to a lack of understanding and appreciation for moral values, as well as the need for teachers to be more consistent in their approach. Cultural and religious diversity in today's educational landscape makes teaching universal ethical values difficult (Chowdhury, 2018). Teachers must be careful when addressing moral issues, as they may face polarization and alienation from students who do not share the same perspective as the school. To fix this, schools should teach kids about respect, justice, sympathy, and the law, and they should also encourage kids to learn about and accept other people's points of view.

Moral education also needs parents and the community to be involved. As Achinstein (2002) discussed in his research, conflicts may arise due to varying opinions, beliefs, and expectations from parents or other community members. Schools must establish good connections with families and the community, allowing open communication and allowing parents to voice their opinions about the role of moral education in the teaching process. Negative peer influence and societal

pressures can also hinder moral education. It is similar to Teo's (2024) work; he said students may find it difficult to relate to moral lessons when facing negative activities like bullying or cheating. Media, social media, and popular cultural trends can also send mixed messages about what is right and wrong. To combat these outside factors, schools can put in place programs that teach kids how to be self-sufficient, strong, and critical thinkers (Spohrer, 2024).

Peer pressure and societal pressures can also cause problems with emotions and behaviour. Schools should establish programs that promote self-awareness, resilience, and critical thinking skills to help students resist these forces and adhere to their moral conduct in difficult situations.

Institutional constraints can also hinder moral education. Many students come to school with emotional and behavioral problems that can prevent them from participating in ethics classes. These issues can range from trauma, bullying, mental health problems, and difficult family situations.

Benefits of moral education

Moral education is a crucial aspect of education, particularly in underserved areas, where character building is often hindered by inadequate facilities and a focus on standardized testing. To address these challenges, schools should advocate for moral and social-emotional education in the curriculum, aligning the objectives of education with the holistic development of the child instead of academically orientated objectives.

One of the main benefits of moral education is the exposure of students to sound principles and well-behaved characters. According to Nucci & Ilten-Gee (2021) basic values such as honesty, integrity, respect, justice, and accountability are taught at an early age, which increase the chances of students being well-behaved in their personal, professional, and academic lives. Students who understand the importance of honesty will act more honestly in their personal, professional, and academic work.

Moral education also improves social relationships and conflict resolution, as it instills sympathy, which is essential for building strong, healthy relationships with others. So, in keeping with Gomez (2024) this sympathy helps students handle peer interaction better at home and in the larger community, leading to better self-control, decreased impulsivity, and increased ability to handle difficult emotions such as anger and frustration. Moral education promotes social responsibility and citizenship, teaching students about justice, fairness, and civic obligation. This fosters a sense of community and encourages students to work towards benefiting society as a whole (Tan, 2018). This sense of social responsibility nurtures individuals into active, engaged individuals dedicated to bettering the world. It is similar to Divecha & Brackett's (2020) work, he said; moral education and social-emotional learning have been empirically validated to decrease the probability of students engaging in problematic behaviors such as delinquency, substance abuse, or bullying.

Ethical education fosters strengthening the character-building process, enhancing the prospects for students to make sound ethical judgements through values such as respect, sympathy, or responsibility.

Improved academic performance is another benefit of moral education. As Purwaningsih (2024) points out in their research, students who receive moral education are motivated to think about their views, actions, and impact on others, leading to critical thinking, learning from failures, and making informed decisions moving forward. Moral education helps students develop a robust moral identity and gain a deeper understanding of their values and perspectives (Kumar, 2024).

Fostering a positive and inclusive school climate is another benefit of moral education. Schools should prioritize moral instruction, encouraging students to practice inclusivity, appreciate variety, and accept opposing viewpoints (Killen & Rutland, 2022). Killen & Rutland (2022) mentioned in their report that cultivating an environment where all students, regardless of their background or differences, are heard and respected reduces bullying, discrimination, and exclusion. Moral education has a long-term impact on society, shaping students into pro-social individuals who contribute to society through their moral values and decision-making skills.

Consistent practice of moral education contributes to a more responsible, empathetic, and fairer society. It also fosters character for future leaders, fostering qualities such as honesty, integrity, justice, and responsibility. Ethics, the foundation of meaningful change in businesses, politics, and community organizations, are essential for leaders to make fair, just, and beneficial decisions. Schools play a crucial role in nurturing the next generation of strong leaders, equipping them with the ethical framework and character necessary for informed, responsible decision-making.

Limitation of the study

This study was designed carefully and carried out in a diligent way, but every research has some limitations. There are lots of external and internal factors that could have interfered with the way of study. Researchers sometimes point out some influential factors below: Firstly, only qualitative methods and purposive sampling are adopted due to the needs of the research. In this type of sampling, it is difficult to generalize it to a large number of populations. Secondly, to conduct this study, data were collected from only 27 samples; if data were collected from more individuals, the results of the study may have been more accurate. Finally, the sample area located in Dhaka has been selected for the research. It would have been more fruitful if the researcher had included different sections of Bangladesh.

Conclusion

In conclusion, moral education helps a child develop generally well and has a big impact on how this child will behave and orient themselves as an adult. As educators who play a vital role in a child's life, they can promote moral values through formal

curriculum, co-curricular activities, and socialisation. Schools have a part to play in building moral values in people by teaching them basic values like justice, accountability, compassion, etc. These values help people become bright members of our society who not only make moral decisions but also have constructive interactions with other intelligent people.

However, for moral education to be positive and effective, schools must implement specific strategies to address the challenges of moral education associated with academic demands, multiculturalism, and outside influences of society. It encourages sympathy, critical thought, and resilience to help students navigate difficult moral dilemmas and social pressures. So long as moral education and social-emotional learning stay front and centre in schools, kids will emerge into adulthood better equipped to perform well in school and make a positive difference in society. Even in a changing, increasingly diverse era, it is necessary to incorporate moral education as part of the school curriculum to enrich the next generations of moral leaders and responsible citizens.

Recommendation

There should be some provisions, like counselors, social workers, or psychologists, in schools to help students deal with the emotional barriers to moral development. For improvement, academic subjects such as science and mathematics should be included in the core curriculum alongside moral education. Students' moral thinking and decision-making skills (values such as justice, integrity, compassion, and respect) should be embedded in everyday conversations through classroom activities and debates, case studies, and real-world situations. To help children develop strong social skills, self-regulation, and emotional intelligence, programmes such as social-emotional learning (SEL) should be improved, which will reduce conflict and create a more welcoming school environment. And it is necessary to establish a school culture that preserves diversity, respect, and emotional safety. One that encourages children to admit and correct their mistakes, as well as benefit from restorative practices, which will increase their empathy and accountability. Teachers, who act as role models in schools, need professional development to enable them to integrate moral education into their daily work and teaching. Moral education requires schools, families, and society to work together consistently to set a standard and reinforce values. Ultimately, schools can help children build a strong moral foundation and be a place for moral learning, while also equipping them with the necessary skills for critical thinking, media literacy, and the experience to evaluate external influences such as peer pressure and cultural norms.

Ethical approval: The research project does not include any animal experiments or human drug experiments. It is a public welfare project, and informed consent is obtained before the research.

Consent to participate: Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in this study.

Availability of data: The author declared that the collected data are original and that all the data were collected by the author. Data is included in the article/supp. Material referenced in the article.

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